

1 **Supercritical anti-solvent fractionation for improving antioxidant and anti-**
2 **inflammatory activities of an *Achillea Millefolium* L. extract**

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23 **Abstract**

24 *Achillea millefolium* L. is a plant widely used in traditional medicine. Nowadays, there is
25 a growing concern about the study of its bioactive properties in order to develop food and
26 nutraceutical formulations. Supercritical anti-solvent fractionation (SAF) of an *A.*
27 *millefolium* extract was carried out to improve its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory
28 activities. A selective precipitation of phenolic compounds was achieved in the
29 precipitation vessel fractions, which presented an antioxidant activity twice than original
30 extract, especially when fractionation was carried out at 10 MPa. The main phenolic
31 components identified in this fraction were luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside, 3,5-dicaffeoylquinic
32 acid, 6-hydroxyluteolin-7-*O*-glucoside and apigenin-7-*O*-glucoside. However, separator
33 fractions presented higher anti-inflammatory activity than precipitation vessel ones,
34 particularly at 15 MPa. This fact could be related to separator fractions enrichment in
35 anti-inflammatory compounds, mainly camphor, artemisia ketone and borneol.
36 Therefore, SAF produced a concentration of antioxidant and anti-inflammatory
37 compounds that could be used as high-added valued ingredients.

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40 **Keywords:** supercritical anti-solvent fractionation, yarrow, antioxidant activity, anti-
41 inflammatory activity, phenolic compounds, bioactive ingredients.

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46 **Abbreviations:** SAF (Supercritical anti-solvent fractionation); DCQA (Dicaffeoylquinic
47 acid); SC-CO₂ (Supercritical CO₂); UAE (Ultrasound-Assisted extraction); GAE (Gallic
48 acid equivalents); THP-1/M (Human THP-1 monocytes differentiated to macrophages).

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50 **1. Introduction**

51 *Achillea millefolium* L. (yarrow) is a flowering plant widely used in folk medicine in
52 Europe. Aqueous and alcoholic extracts from dried upper parts of yarrow have been
53 employed in the treatment of digestive problems, hepato-biliary disorders and externally,
54 for the treatment of skin and mucous membrane inflammation (Dias et al., 2013). The
55 study of this plant, both its composition and biological activities, has awakened a growing
56 interest in order to develop pharmaceutical, food and nutraceutical products. Vitas,
57 Cvetanović, Mašković, Švarc-Gajić & Malbaša (2018) produced kombucha beverages
58 from a yarrow infusion and extracts. In addition, nowadays there are on the market several
59 herbal tea mixtures (containing yarrow), mainly indicated for digestive problems.

60 Certain naturally occurring bioactive compounds present in *A. millefolium*, such as
61 phenolic compounds, particularly chlorogenic and dicaffeoylquinic acids (DCQA) and
62 flavonoids, as well as those belonging to the volatile oil fraction have been associated
63 with health benefits (Mohammadhosseini, Sarker, & Akbarzadeh, 2017). Moreover,
64 recent reports indicated that *Achillea* genus presents an important antioxidant activity,
65 related to its flavonoids and total phenolic content (Giorgi, Mingozi, Madeo, Speranza,
66 & Cocucci, 2009; Mohammadhosseini et al., 2017). In addition, Trumbeckaite et al.
67 (2011) reported that the radical-scavenging properties of a hydroalcoholic extract of *A.*
68 *millefolium* were related to the presence of luteolin and chlorogenic acid in the extract, an
69 in a lesser extent, to the presence of rutin and luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside. *A. millefolium*
70 extracts have also been reported to present anti-inflammatory activity (Tadić et al., 2017).
71 Moreover, Kazemi (2015) showed that an *A. millefolium* essential oil, with high quantities
72 of thymol and borneol, was able to inhibit nitric oxide production in macrophages
73 stimulated with LPS (lipopolysaccharide).

74 Different approaches have been carried out in order to obtain fractions with high
75 concentrations of phenolic compounds or essential oils components than original plants
76 extracts; such as applying anion exchange resins (Kammerer, Boschet, Kammerer, &
77 Carle, 2011), high pressure techniques (Fernández-Ponce, Casas, Mantell, & de la Ossa,
78 2015), membrane separation (Cissé, Vaillant, Pallet, & Dornier, 2011), supercritical fluid
79 extraction with fractionation (Reverchon, & de Marco, 2006) or chromatography methods
80 (Pedan, Fischer, & Rohn, 2016; Shaheen, Lu, Geng, Shao & Wei, 2017). Recently,
81 supercritical anti-solvent fractionation (SAF) has been proposed for the fractionation of
82 complex plants extracts. In addition, the use of carbon dioxide as a supercritical fluid
83 offers many advantages, such as the low critical temperature of CO₂ and the absence of
84 oxygen during extraction, which allows minimize or avoid the degradation of solutes, as
85 well as the possibility of recovering a free-solvent fraction (Wijngaard, Hossain, Rai, &
86 Brunton, 2012). In the SAF process, a polar liquid solution of a plant extract, containing
87 several families of compounds, is sprayed continuously in a co-current with supercritical
88 CO₂ (SC-CO₂), which acts as antisolvent. This contact allows the precipitation of more
89 polar components from the liquid solution, insoluble in SC-CO₂, whereas the remaining
90 compounds, that are mainly less polar components, remained dissolved and are recovered
91 by downstream pressure reduction (Meneses, Caputo, Scognamiglio, Reverchon, &
92 Adami, 2015).

93 For that matter, SAF technique has recently used to fractionate phenolic compounds from
94 plants extracts. Therefore, Natolino, Da Porto, Rodríguez-Rojo, Moreno & Cocero (2016)
95 used this technique to obtain fractions enriched in polyphenols from a grape marc extract.
96 Operating at 12MPa, 45 °C and 0.99 CO₂ molar fraction, they obtained fractions with a
97 relative enrichment of 350% of total polyphenols and a proanthocyanidins enrichment
98 between 300-450%. Visentín, Cismondi, & Maestri (2011) also applied the SAF to

99 improve carnosic acid (CA) recovery from an ethanolic extract of rosemary leaves,
100 obtaining two different fractions, one insoluble with low concentration in CA (<5%) and
101 another resinous extract with 33% of CA. Moreover, Villanueva et al. (2015) carried out
102 the fractionation of green tea extracts obtaining decaffeinated fractions with high
103 concentration in catechins.

104 Nevertheless, there are only few studies relating the enrichment in phenolic compounds
105 or essential oil components of the fractions obtained by this technique, with their
106 biological activities. Chinnarasu et al. (2015) obtained precipitates with high antioxidant
107 activity from the fractionation of olive leaves extracts and Marqués, Porta, Reverchon,
108 Renuncio and Mainar (2013) concentrated antioxidants from a defatted grape seed waste
109 extract, achieving concentrations up to 2.7 higher than those in the starting solution.
110 Sánchez-Camargo et al. (2016) also enhanced the antiproliferative activity of a rosemary
111 fraction enriched in carnosic acid and carnosol.

112 In this context, and based on a previous work (Villanueva-Bermejo et al., 2017), the aim
113 of the present study was to improve the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities of an
114 *A. millefolium* extract using SAF technology. Besides, the original extract and fractions
115 obtained were analyzed in order to relate its chemical composition with the biological
116 activities found.

117

118 **2. Materials and methods**

119 2.1. Reagents and chemicals

120 Ethanol (99.5% purity) and Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent were obtained from Panreac
121 (Barcelona, Spain). (±)-6-Hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchromane-2-carboxylic acid
122 (Trolox), 2,2'-Azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) diammonium salt
123 (ABTS), gallic acid for titration (> 97.5%), potassium persulfate (99.9%) and thiazolyl

124 blue tetrazolium bromide (MTT) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Madrid, Spain).
125 Formic acid (99%) was obtained from Acros Organics (Madrid, Spain) and acetonitrile
126 HPLC grade from Macron Fine Chemicals (Madrid, Spain). Reference standards for
127 phenolic compounds, such as chlorogenic acid, cryptochlorogenic acid, diosmetin, ferulic
128 acid, neochlorogenic acid, rosmarinic acid and vitexin (all analytical standard or HPLC
129 purity $\geq 95\%$) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). 1,5-Dicaffeoylquinic
130 acid (DCQA), 3,4-DCQA, 3,5-DCQA, 4,5-DCQA, apigenin, caftaric acid, casticin,
131 luteolin, orientin, schaftoside and vicenin II were obtained from Phytolab (Madrid,
132 Spain). Finally, amentoflavone, apigenin-7-*O*-glucoside, caffeic acid, homoorientin,
133 luteolin-7-*O*- β -D-glucoside, quercetin and rutin were obtained from Extrasynthese S.A.
134 (Genay, France) and luteolin-7-*O*- β -D-glucuronide from HWI Analytic GmbH
135 (Rülzheim, Germany). The water used in this study was ultrapure type 1 (Millipore,
136 Madrid, Spain). CO₂ (N38) was purchased from Carbueros Metalicos (Madrid, Spain).

137

138 2.2. Yarrow samples and Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction (UAE)

139 *A. millefolium* from Bulgaria was supplied by a local herbalist (Murcia, Spain). According
140 to supplier specifications, the sample included inflorescences and upper dried leaves of
141 the plant (harvested in spring) and sun-dried (water content < than 5% wt). The plant was
142 ground using a Premill 250 hammer mill (Leal S.A., Granollers, Spain) and sieved
143 (particle size < 500 μm). UAE plant extraction was carried out by using an ultrasonic
144 device (Branson Digital Sonifier 250, Danbury, USA) with a power of 200 W and
145 frequencies of 60 kHz. Extraction conditions employed were ethanol as extraction solvent
146 (1:10 plant/solvent ratio), 30 min time, 40 °C temperature and an output of 70% with
147 respect to the nominal amplitude. Finally, the extract was concentrated, until the final

148 volume contained 17.9 mg/mL of total solid concentration (2.3% wt.) by rotary
149 evaporation and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until its use in the SAF process.

150

151 2.3. SAF process

152 A detailed explanation of the device and the process design employed can be found
153 elsewhere (Villanueva-Bermejo et al., 2017). Briefly, fractionation of UAE yarrow
154 solution (concentration of 17.9 mg/mL) was carried out at two different pressures (10 and
155 15 MPa), $40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and CO_2 /extract flow ratio of 31.3 g/g (50 g/min for CO_2 and 1.6 g/min
156 for UAE extract). The experiment started by pumping SC- CO_2 into the precipitation
157 vessel until the pressure and temperature conditions were attained. Then, the UAE yarrow
158 solution was pumped into the precipitator. After mixing, the yarrow extract components
159 that were not soluble in SC- CO_2 + ethanol mixture precipitated in the precipitation vessel
160 and were collected (precipitation vessel fraction). The fraction soluble in SC- CO_2 +
161 ethanol went to separators where reduced pressure turned CO_2 into a gas and this fraction
162 together with ethanol was also collected. The samples obtained in both separators were
163 combined in a single fraction and ethanol removed by rotary evaporation under vacuum
164 (separator fraction). Fractions were kept at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ under darkness until analysis.

165

166 2.4. HPLC-PAD-ESI-QTOF-MS analysis

167 Phenolic compounds were analyzed by HPLC following the chromatographic method
168 developed by Villalva et al. (2018). An Agilent HPLC 1260 Infinity series system
169 (Agilent Technologies Inc., Santa Clara, CA, USA) was used for that purpose.
170 Chromatographic separation was carried out by using a reverse phase ACE Excell 3 Super
171 C18 column (150 mm x 4.6 mm, 3 μm particle size) from Advanced Chromatography
172 Technologies (Aberdeen, Scotland) protected by an ACE 3 C18-AR (10 mm x 3 mm)

173 guard column. Dry samples were dissolved in ethanol to reach a 5 mg/mL concentration
174 and filtered by 0.45 μm polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) filter before injection (20 μL).
175 Retention time and UV-Vis spectrum of each chromatographic peak was compared with
176 analytical standards for identification purpose; moreover, accurate mass from HPLC-ESI-
177 QTOF-MS in negative mode analysis was used for compounds assignment.
178 Compounds quantification was carried out by using calibration curves from analytical
179 standard, as previously described in Villalva et al. (2018). In addition, luteolin-6,8-di-*C*-
180 glucoside, 6-hydroxyluteolin-7-*O*-glucoside and non-identified flavones were quantified
181 by the calibration curve of orientin, luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside and luteolin respectively.
182 Likewise, schaftoside and vicenin II calibration curves were used for schaftoside isomer
183 and apigenin-*C*-hexoside-*C*-pentoside quantification.

184

185 2.5. GC-MS analysis of the separator fractions

186 The analysis of the UAE extract and SAF fractions collected from the separator was
187 carried out in an Agilent 7890A system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA).
188 The unit comprised a split/splitless injector, a FID detector and a mass spectrometer
189 detector (5975C triple-axis). The analysis was performed using an Agilent HP-5MS
190 capillary column (30 m \times 0.25 mm i.d., 0.25 μm phase thickness) and the following
191 chromatographic method: 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ initial temperature, from 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 3 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$,
192 isothermal at 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 min, then increased from 150 to 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 6 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ and
193 finally isothermal at 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 min. Samples were dissolved in ethanol (at 5 mg/mL),
194 filtered by 0.45 μm filters and injected (1 μL) in splitless mode. Helium (99.99 %) was
195 employed as carrier gas (1 mL/min flow rate). The temperatures used were 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the
196 injector and 230, 280 and 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the mass spectrometer ion source, interface and
197 quadrupole, respectively. The mass spectrometer operated under electron impact mode

198 (70 eV) and it was used in total ion current (TIC) mode (mass range from 40 to 500 m/z).
199 The identification of compounds was performed by matching the mass spectral
200 fragmentation patterns with the Wiley 229 mass spectral library, as well as comparing
201 their corresponding retention index to those reported in the literature. Analyses were
202 done in triplicate.

203

204 2.6. Determination of total phenolic content (TPC) and antioxidant activity

205 TPC determination was carried out according to Folin-Ciocalteu reagent method as
206 described by Singleton, Orthofer & Lamuela-Reventos (1999) using gallic acid as
207 standard. In brief, 10 μ l of samples (5 mg/mL for all samples, except for P10 and P15
208 which working solution was 3 mg/mL) were mixed with 50 μ L of Folin-Ciocalteu
209 reagent and 790 μ L of deionized water. After 3 min, 150 μ L of sodium carbonate solution
210 (20% w/v) were added and mixed. After 2h, the absorbance at 760 nm was recorded. The
211 results were expressed as mg of gallic acid equivalents (GAE)/g dry sample. Analyses
212 were performed at least in triplicate.

213 The antioxidant activity was measured using the ABTS^{•+} radical scavenging assay as
214 described in Re et al. (1999). The reaction was placed with 990 μ L of the diluted ABTS^{•+}
215 radical solution and 10 μ L of plant extract dilutions in order to achieve a 20% to 80% of
216 radical inhibition (sample concentration varying from 5 mg/mL to 20 mg/mL). The
217 reaction was allowed to stand until the absorbance reached a plateau, and the absorbance
218 was recorded at 734 nm. Results were expressed as mmol Trolox equivalent/g dry sample
219 (TEAC value). Analyses were done at least in triplicate.

220

221 2.7. Anti-inflammatory activity

222 Human THP-1 monocytes (ATCC, Manassas, VA, USA) were plated at a density of
223 5×10^5 cells/mL in 24 wells plates. Culture medium consisted in RPMI 1640 supplemented
224 with 10% FBS, 100 U/mL penicillin, 100 mg/mL streptomycin, 2 mM L-glutamine
225 (Gibco, Paisley, UK) and 0.05 mM β -mercaptoethanol (Sigma-Aldrich, Madrid, Spain)
226 at 37 °C in 95% humidified air containing 5% CO₂. Monocytes differentiation to
227 macrophages (THP-1/M cells) was induced by maintaining the cells with 100 ng/ml of
228 phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) (Sigma-Aldrich, Madrid, Spain) for 48 h. THP-
229 1/M cells viability, in presence of yarrow extract or fractions, was tested by MTT assay
230 following Mosmann (1983) method. The assays were performed in triplicate.
231 After differentiation, THP-1/M cells were washed with PBS and incubated with 0.05
232 μ g/mL of LPS from E. Coli O55:B5 (Sigma-Aldrich, Spain) in presence of yarrow extract
233 or fractions for 24 h. Then, the supernatants were collected and frozen at -20 °C. An anti-
234 inflammatory drug, indomethacin (5 μ g/mL), was used as a reference.
235 ELISA kits (BD Biosciences, Aalst, Belgium), according to manufacturer's instructions,
236 were used to measure the release of TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6 in the supernatants of THP-
237 1/M cells. The quantification was carried out at 450 nm with substrate correction at 570
238 nm using a multiscanner autoreader (InfiniteM200 Tecan, Barcelona, Spain). The results
239 were expressed as the mean of three determinations \pm standard deviation.

240

241 2.8. Statistical analysis

242 Statistical analysis was performed using Statgraphics v. Centurion XVI package for
243 Windows (Statpoint Inc., Warrenton, VA, USA). Statistical differences between samples
244 were analyzed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Fisher's least significant
245 difference (LSD) procedure was applied to determine significant differences between
246 means at $p \leq 0.05$.

247

248 **3. Results and discussion**

249 **3.1. TPC content and antioxidant activity of yarrow extract and SAF fractions.**

250 UAE extracts from yarrow were carried out using ethanol as extraction solvent, at 40 °C
251 and 30 min. Previous studies carried out in the research group (data not shown) showed
252 that those conditions were the most appropriated to obtain extracts with a high content of
253 TPC and an important antioxidant activity. Thus, this UAE extract (called original
254 extract) presented a yield of $5.7 \pm 0.9\%$ (% dry wt.), a TPC of 54.30 ± 1.07 mg GAE/g
255 extract and a TEAC value of 0.173 ± 0.004 mmol Trolox/g extract.

256 SAF process was carried out in order to enhance the antioxidant activity of this extract.
257 Consequently, two different experiments, at 10 and 15 MPa of pressure, 40 °C and
258 CO₂/extract flow ratio of 31.3 g/g, were developed. These conditions were based in a
259 previous work (Villanueva-Bermejo et al., 2017).

260 Fractions obtained at 10 and 15 MPa from the precipitation vessel (called P10 and P15)
261 and separators (called S10 and S15) were collected and its yield value, TPC content and
262 antioxidant activity were determined (Table 1). Results indicated that SAF process
263 achieved an important phenolic compounds enrichment in the precipitation vessel
264 fractions. It is worth to mention that this enrichment was significantly higher when used
265 pressure was 10 MPa, where P10 fraction presented an antioxidant activity 2-fold superior
266 than the original extract. Regarding separator fractions, S10 and S15 showed a similar
267 antioxidant activity and near 5-fold lower than original extract. This result was related to
268 the lower quantity of TPC presented in these fractions.

269 Therefore, phenolic composition of the original extract and fractions were analyzed in
270 order to establish a relationship between its composition and the antioxidant activity
271 found.

272

273 **3.2. Phenolic characterization of yarrow extract and SAF fractions.**

274 The HPLC analysis of phenolic compounds in the original extract and SAF fractions are
275 shown in Table 2. The main compounds identified in the original extract were flavonoids,
276 either in glycosylated or in aglycone form, and phenolic acids. Therefore, the compounds
277 presented in higher concentration corresponded to the flavonoids luteolin and its
278 glycosylated form (luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside), as well as the dicaffeoylquinic acids, where
279 the 3,5-DCQA stood out. These results are in agreement with others previously
280 reported, where the main flavonoids found in several yarrow extracts were luteolin-7-*O*-
281 glucoside, luteolin, apigenin-7-*O*-glucoside and apigenin, while within the
282 dicaffeoylquinic acids, 3,5-DCQA was the one in a greater extent (Benedek, Gjoncaj,
283 Saukei, & Kopp, 2007; Vitalini et al., 2011). Related to precipitation vessel fractions, its
284 principal components were luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside, 3,5-DCQA, luteolin, apigenin-7-*O*-
285 glucoside and 6-hydroxyluteolin-7-*O*-glucoside, representing between 73% (P10) and
286 60% (P15) of all phenolic compounds identified. Meanwhile, separator fractions
287 contained a reduced quantity of phenolic compounds, where flavonoids aglycones
288 stood out.

289 Precipitation vessel fractions and the original sample presented a similar phenolic
290 composition, although the compounds concentration in the fractions was, in general,
291 much higher, highlighting luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside and 3,5-DCQA. These results could be
292 related to the low solubility of glycosylated flavonoids and phenolic acids in the SC-CO₂
293 + ethanol mixture, since these compounds are poorly soluble in low-polar solvents
294 (Chebil et al., 2007). On the other hand, the flavonoids aglycones, as less polar
295 compounds, would be more soluble in the mixture SC-CO₂ + ethanol and therefore they
296 would be dragged to the separator fraction.

297 However, it should be noted that there were some differences between fractions P10 and
298 P15, since P10 fraction presented a greater amount of luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside and 3,5-
299 DCQA than P15 fraction, whereas P15 contained a higher quantity of luteolin and
300 apigenin than P10. These results could indicate that an increase in pressure during the
301 fractionation process, would increment the presence of aglycones in the precipitation
302 vessel fraction. In order to explain these results, it must be taken into account the complex
303 multicomponent structure of extracts, comprising substances in a wide polarity range and
304 with different solubility in SC-CO₂, which could exert a strong effect regarding the partial
305 solubility of compounds involved and their precipitation behavior. Nevertheless,
306 observing the solubility behavior of pure compounds in SC-CO₂, it can be established
307 that in the case of more polar compounds (e.g. hydroxycinnamic acids) an increase of
308 pressure from 10 to 15 MPa resulted in 4.4-5.4 solubility increase (Murga, Sanz, Beltran
309 & Cabeza, 2003), while for less polar compounds (e.g. quercetin) this ratio was about 3.0-
310 3.5 (Chafer, Fornari, Berna & Stateva, 2004). Thus, according to the pure component
311 solubility behavior, an increase of the precipitation pressure could increase the recovery
312 of aglycones in precipitation vessel.

313 Thus, the higher antioxidant activity found in P10 and P15, compared to original extract,
314 could be related with the significant increase in several phenolic compounds found in
315 these fractions, mainly luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside, 3,5-DCQA, luteolin (only in P15),
316 apigenin-7-*O*-glucoside and 6-hydroxyluteolin-7-*O*-glucoside. Besides, when comparing
317 P10 and P15, it can be observed that P10, with the higher antioxidant activity, also
318 presented the higher quantity of luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside and 3,5-DCQA (representing
319 almost 55% of the fraction). Kim et al. (2011) indicated that 3,5-DCQA presented an
320 important antioxidant activity, significantly higher than chlorogenic acid. Besides, the
321 antioxidant activity of luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside have also been reported (Song & Park,

2014; Antonisamy et al., 2016). However, it must be taken into account that this fact could be also due to synergies among all the phenolic compounds found in P10 fraction.

324

3.3. Anti-inflammatory activity of yarrow extract and SAF fractions.

First, original extract and SAF fractions were evaluated for cytotoxicity on THP-1/M cells by MTT method. Results showed that, at the higher concentration used in the anti-inflammatory assays, 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, neither original extract nor SAF fractions presented cytotoxicity (cell viability $\geq 95\%$). Indomethacin at 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ also presented no cytotoxicity.

The activation of THP-1/M was carried out with the addition of LPS to the medium. Fig. 1 showed that these LPS treated cells (positive control), after an incubation period of 24h, presented an important increase in the release of TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6, compared to non-activated controls (negative control). When THP-1/M were activated with LPS in presence of 5 and 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of original extract and SAF fractions, a decrease in TNF- α secreted level was observed (Fig. 1), compared with positive control. Moreover, 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of original extract inhibited TNF- α secretion in a 40%. Regarding P10 and P15 fractions, P15 presented a decrease in TNF- α superior to P10 and similar to that obtained with original extract. However, it should be noted that the greatest decrease in TNF- α secretion was achieved in presence of S10 and S15 fractions. Thus, 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of S15 fraction reduced TNF- α release in a 70%.

In the same way, the original extract and SAF fractions inhibited the IL-1 β secretion by activated cells, at both concentrations employed, although separator fractions showed the greatest inhibition (Fig. 1). Thus, meanwhile 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of original extract decrease IL-1 β release in a 40%, the same concentration of S15 showed an inhibition near to 70%. In addition, 5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of S15 reduced IL-1 β secretion by a 60%. The obtained results for the

347 IL-6 release in presence of samples (Fig. 1) were similar to those obtained for TNF- α and
348 IL-1 β , since S10 and S15 fractions were the most active and produced an important
349 decrease in the IL-6 release (near to basal levels).

350 These results indicated that all SAF fractions presented anti-inflammatory activity,
351 although separator fractions were much more active than precipitation vessel ones. The
352 anti-inflammatory activity of precipitation vessel fractions could be related to its content
353 in phenolic compounds, more specifically with dicaffeoylquinic acids, luteolin, apigenin
354 and its glycosides, since the anti-inflammatory effects of these compounds have been
355 previously described (Liang & Kitts, 2016; Wang et al, 2014; Wang et al., 2017).
356 Moreover, Francisco et al. (2014) indicated that luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside presented a
357 certain anti-inflammatory activity, but lower than that observed with the luteolin aglycone
358 in LPS-stimulated macrophages. Similarly, Choi et al. (2014) reported that apigenin
359 presented higher anti-inflammatory activity than other naturally occurring C-glycosylated
360 derivatives of apigenin. These results could explain the higher inhibition of TNF- α , IL-
361 1 β and IL-6 secretion found when using P15 compared with P10, since P15 contained a
362 higher amount of luteolin and apigenin aglycones, whereas P10 presented a higher
363 quantity of luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside and apigenin-7-*O*-glucoside.

364 However, the higher anti-inflammatory activity found in separator fractions, could not be
365 related to its phenolic compounds content, due to the low quantity of these compounds
366 presented in these fractions. Thereby, it's relevant to notice that conditions used to obtain
367 the separator fractions allowed the enhancement of these fractions in essential oil
368 components. Since essential oils from *A. millefolium* have been reported to present anti-
369 inflammatory activity (Chou, Peng, Hsu, Lin & Shih, 2013; Kazemi, 2015), S10 and S15
370 were analyzed by GC-MS in order to establish a relationship between the composition
371 and the anti-inflammatory activity of these fractions.

372

373 **3.4. GC-MS characterization of separator fractions**

374 In order to identify the compounds involved in the anti-inflammatory activity found in
375 separator fractions (S10 and S15), a characterization by GC-MS of these fractions, along
376 with the original extract was performed. The identification of the main volatile
377 compounds presented in the sample (Table 3) was performed based on the comparison of
378 their mass spectra and retention index (RI). As can be observed, 30 identified and 2 non-
379 identified compounds were found in S10 and S15. In general, a very similar GC-MS
380 profile was obtained for both fractions, being camphor, artemisia ketone, borneol and 2,6-
381 dimethyl-1,7-octadiene-3,6-diol the most abundant compounds in both fractions. Original
382 yarrow extract also presented a similar profile to S10 and S15, although total
383 chromatographic area (expressed as Σ AUC) was much higher for the fractions. As
384 expected, separator fractions have been enriched in essential oil components (1.75 times
385 for S10 and 2.18 for S15), in comparison to the original extract. Regarding main
386 components, camphor and borneol were shown to reduce TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6
387 secretion in THP-1 macrophages stimulated with LPS or ox-LDL (oxidized low-density
388 lipoproteins) (Arranz et al., 2014a; Arranz et al., 2014b). Similarly, Rungqu et al. (2016)
389 reported that an essential oil containing a 37.5% of artemisia ketone presented an
390 important anti-inflammatory activity, evaluated in rats, using egg albumin-induced paw
391 edema. Therefore, the anti-inflammatory activity exhibited by S10 and S15 fractions
392 could be mainly related to the presence of these three compounds (camphor, borneol and
393 artemisia ketone) that represented approximately 30% of the fractions. However, the
394 contribution to other anti-inflammatory compounds presented in smaller quantities, such
395 as eucalyptol and β -linalool, to this activity cannot be ruled out. Thus, the enrichment of
396 S10 and S15 fractions in compounds that exhibit anti-inflammatory activity, regarding to

397 the original extract, would explain the higher anti-inflammatory activity of these
398 fractions. Accordingly, S15 fraction that presented a higher enrichment in essential oil
399 compounds than S10, also presented a higher anti-inflammatory activity.

400

401 **Conclusion**

402 Supercritical anti-solvent fractionation of an ethanolic yarrow extract resulted an
403 adequate method to improve its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities. Thus, a
404 selective precipitation of phenolic compounds increased its antioxidant activity twice,
405 compared to original extract, especially when fractionation was carried out at 10 MPa.
406 Regarding anti-inflammatory activity, separator fractions presented higher anti-
407 inflammatory activity than precipitation vessel ones. This fact was related to separator
408 fractions enrichment in essential oil compounds with anti-inflammatory activity. Being
409 more active, in this case, the separator fraction obtained when pressure was 15 MPa.
410 Therefore, this study pointed out the feasibility of SAF process as a green technology in
411 order to achieve a fractionation of compounds with different biological activities. This
412 fact could be a useful tool for food or nutraceutical products design.

413

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602 **Table 1.** Yield values (mass precipitated/mass of solid pumped), TPC content and
 603 antioxidant activity (TEAC value) in original extract and SAF fractions: P10
 604 (precipitation vessel fraction at 10 MPa), P15 (precipitation vessel fraction at 15 MPa,
 605 S10 (separator fraction at 10 MPa) and S15 (separator fraction at 15 MPa). Data shown
 606 represents mean \pm S.D. (n=3).

Sample	Yield (%)	TPC (mg GAE/g)	TEAC value (mmol Trolox/g)
Original extract	5.7 \pm 0.9	54.30 \pm 1.07 ^c	0.173 \pm 0.004 ^c
P-10	6.6 \pm 1.1	136.44 \pm 1.28 ^a	0.345 \pm 0.002 ^a
S-10	52.1 \pm 5.3	30.30 \pm 0.25 ^d	0.035 \pm 0.002 ^d
P-15	13.3 \pm 2.4	119.20 \pm 2.23 ^b	0.317 \pm 0.003 ^b
S-15	42.6 \pm 4.2	23.83 \pm 0.85 ^e	0.033 \pm 0.002 ^d

607 ^{a,b,c,d,e} Different superscript letters denote statistical differences between samples within
 608 the same column. Significance level at $p \leq 0.05$ with Fisher's Least Significant
 609 Difference (LSD) test.

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621 **Table 2.** Phenolic composition of original extract and SAF fractions (mg compound/g
622 dry fraction). P10 (precipitation vessel fraction at 10 MPa), P15 (precipitation vessel
623 fraction at 15 MPa), S10 (separator fraction at 10 MPa) and S15 (separator fraction at 15
624 MPa). Data shown represents mean \pm S.D. (n=3).

Compound	Original	P-10	S-10	P-15	S-15
Neochlorogenic acid	0.06 \pm 0.00	0.18 \pm 0.00 ^a	-	0.14 \pm 0.00 ^b	-
Caftaric acid	< L.Q.	0.18 \pm 0.00 ^b	-	0.22 \pm 0.00 ^a	-
Chlorogenic acid	0.62 \pm 0.00	2.32 \pm 0.0 ^a	0.10 \pm 0.00 [*]	1.91 \pm 0.04 ^b	-
Cryptochlorogenic acid	0.01 \pm 0.01	0.03 \pm 0.00 ^a	-	0.04 \pm 0.01 ^a	-
Vicenin II	0.37 \pm 0.01	1.61 \pm 0.00 ^a	-	1.12 \pm 0.01 ^b	-
Caffeic acid	0.17 \pm 0.00	-	0.19 \pm 0.00 ^A	-	0.18 \pm 0.00 ^B
Schaftoside isomer	0.26 \pm 0.00	1.49 \pm 0.05 ^a	-	0.90 \pm 0.00 ^b	-
Schaftoside	0.27 \pm 0.00	1.36 \pm 0.00 ^a	-	0.89 \pm 0.00 ^b	-
Homoorientin	0.02 \pm 0.01	0.32 \pm 0.00 ^a	-	0.16 \pm 0.00 ^b	-
Apigenin-C-hexoside -C-pentoside	0.30 \pm 0.00	1.43 \pm 0.01 ^a	-	0.85 \pm 0.00 ^b	-
Luteolin-6,8-di-C-glucoside	0.47 \pm 0.00	2.39 \pm 0.01 ^a	-	1.51 \pm 0.00 ^b	-
6-hydroxyluteolin-7-O-glucoside	1.45 \pm 0.01	7.65 \pm 0.02 ^a	0.02 \pm 0.00 [*]	4.66 \pm 0.00 ^b	-
Rutin	0.51 \pm 0.01	1.44 \pm 0.00 ^a	-	1.34 \pm 0.02 ^b	-
Vitexin	0.13 \pm 0.01	0.15 \pm 0.00 ^b	-	0.25 \pm 0.01 ^a	-
Luteolin-7-O-glucoside	7.69 \pm 0.08	33.2 \pm 0.07 ^a	0.39 \pm 0.00 [*]	23.9 \pm 0.97 ^b	-
Luteolin-7-B-glucuronide	0.20 \pm 0.01	0.56 \pm 0.00 ^a	-	0.59 \pm 0.03 ^a	-
Ferulic acid	0.08 \pm 0.02	0.09 \pm 0.00 ^a	-	0.04 \pm 0.00 ^b	-
3,4-DCQA	0.38 \pm 0.05	1.23 \pm 0.00 ^a	-	0.69 \pm 0.00 ^b	-
1,5-DCQA	0.69 \pm 0.01	2.86 \pm 0.01 ^a	-	1.80 \pm 0.09 ^b	-
3,5-DCQA	3.62 \pm 0.02	17.8 \pm 0.03 ^a	0.28 \pm 0.01 ^A	11.6 \pm 0.10 ^b	0.10 \pm 0.00 ^B
Apigenin-7-O-glucoside	1.79 \pm 0.01	6.89 \pm 0.03 ^a	0.32 \pm 0.00 [*]	5.88 \pm 0.01 ^b	-
4,5-DCQA	0.97 \pm 0.01	4.30 \pm 0.01 ^a	0.05 \pm 0.00 [*]	3.19 \pm 0.00 ^b	-
Rosmarinic acid	0.18 \pm 0.00	-	-	-	-
Luteolin	4.47 \pm 0.01	4.58 \pm 0.01 ^b	3.18 \pm 0.00 ^A	13.0 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.95 \pm 0.01 ^B
Quercetin	0.47 \pm 0.00	0.68 \pm 0.00 ^b	0.32 \pm 0.01 [*]	1.44 \pm 0.01 ^a	-
Flavone n.i.	1.66 \pm 0.00	1.15 \pm 0.00 ^b	1.42 \pm 0.00 ^A	3.33 \pm 0.00 ^a	1.16 \pm 0.00 ^B
Apigenin	1.96 \pm 0.00	1.00 \pm 0.00 ^b	1.83 \pm 0.00 ^A	4.74 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.93 \pm 0.00 ^B
Diosmetin	0.50 \pm 0.00	0.31 \pm 0.00 ^b	0.53 \pm 0.00 ^A	0.73 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.50 \pm 0.00 ^B
Amentoflavone	0.42 \pm 0.00	0.16 \pm 0.00 ^b	0.52 \pm 0.00 ^B	0.41 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.62 \pm 0.00 ^A
Flavone n.i.	2.14 \pm 0.00	0.57 \pm 0.00 ^a	2.68 \pm 0.00 ^B	0.57 \pm 0.00 ^a	3.68 \pm 0.00 ^A
Casticin	0.29 \pm 0.00	-	0.44 \pm 0.01 ^B	-	0.62 \pm 0.01 ^A

625 < L.Q.: below limit of quantification. * An asterisk indicates statistical differences between
626 original extract and fractions. ^{a,b} Different lowercase letters denote statistical differences
627 between P10 and P15 fractions. ^{A,B} Different capital letters denote statistical differences
628 between S10 and S15 fractions. Significance level at $p \leq 0.05$ with Fisher's Least
629 Significant Difference (LSD) test.

Table 3. GC-MS identification, peak area contribution (%), and retention index (RI) of compounds found in original extract and separator fractions. S10 (separator fraction at 10 MPa) and S15 (separator fraction at 15 MPa).

RI	Compound	Original	S10	S15
997	Yomogi alcohol	2.1	2.0	2.2
1028	Eucalyptol	4.3	3.5	3.4
1037	γ -Vinyl- γ -valerolactone	1.8	1.6	1.5
1058	Artemisia ketone	11.0	9.9	9.4
1070	1,2-Epoxylinool	0.9	0.8	0.8
1079	Artemisia alcohol	1.0	0.8	0.8
1084	<i>cis</i> -Linalool oxide	0.8	0.6	0.7
1099	β -Linalool	0.9	0.9	0.9
1136	Camphor	13.8	12.5	12.3
1141	<i>cis</i> -Verbenol	0.9	0.7	0.7
1160	Borneol	8.7	8.9	8.6
1171	2-Methyl-2-octen-4-ol	1.0	0.9	1.0
1174	Terpinene-4-ol	0.5	0.4	0.5
1182	<i>p</i> -Cymen-8-ol	0.7	0.8	0.9
1188	3,7-dimethyl-1,5-Octadiene-3,7-diol	5.9	6.1	6.2
1200	Verbenone	0.5	0.6	0.6
1212	Fragranol	0.4	0.4	0.4
1218	2-Hydroxycineole	0.6	0.6	0.7
1236	<i>trans</i> -Chrysanthenyl acetate	2.4	2.5	2.5
1250	Piperitone	0.9	0.9	1.0
1261	(<i>5E</i>)-5,9-Dimethyl-5,8-decadien-2-one	1.5	1.4	1.3
1276	2,6-Dimethyl-1,7-octadiene-3,6-diol	8.6	9.3	9.3
1280	Bornyl acetate	0.8	1.0	1.0
1284	n.i.	7.2	8.7	8.5
1393	Jasmone	1.6	1.6	1.5
1412	β -Caryophyllene	1.4	1.6	1.5
1569	Spathulenol	0.9	1.2	1.1
1578	Caryophyllene oxide	4.9	6.0	5.8
1640	β -Eudesmol	1.2	1.2	1.5
1810	Saussurea lactone	3.4	3.2	3.2
1845	Hexahydrofarnesyl acetone	3.0	3.2	3.4
2069	n.i.	6.5	6.2	6.7
Σ AUC		24.41 10⁶	42.80 10⁶	53.40 10⁶

630 n.i.: no identified; AUC (area under curve)

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636 Figure legends

637 **Figure 1.** Levels of TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL6 secreted by THP-1/M activated with LPS in
638 presence of original extract and SAF fractions. Positive control: cells stimulated with LPS
639 but in absence of extract. Negative control: cells in contact just with RPMI media. Ind.:
640 Indomethacin. Original: original yarrow extract. P10: precipitation vessel fraction at 10
641 MPa. P15: precipitation vessel fraction at 15 MPa. S10: separator fraction at 10 MPa.
642 S15: separator fraction at 15 MPa. Each bar is the mean of three determinations \pm S.D.
643 *Denotes statistical differences when compares with positive control. ^{a,b,c,d} Different
644 lowercase letters indicate statistical differences between samples at 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. ^{A,B,C,D}
645 Different capital letters indicate statistical differences between samples at 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$.
646 Significance level at $p \leq 0.05$ with Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) test.

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661 Figure 1.

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